

COMPRESSION FAILURE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITE CYLINDRICAL SHELLS UNDER AXIAL LOADING

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SUMMARY: This paper addresses failure characterisation and prediction for moderately thin-walled carbon fibre/epoxy cylinders subjected to compressive axial loads. Specimens of [02/902]_s configuration failed in a local buckling mode, with virtually no prebuckling acoustic activity. In the case of the [90/45/-45/0]_{as} laminates there was moderate acoustic activity at load levels as low as 40% of the final failure load, suggesting that damage was occurring within the laminate well before the final failure in a buckling related mode. The [45/-45/45/-45]_s specimens demonstrated significant acoustic activity from low load levels and failed by material fracture. A finite element analysis based design methodology is presented which considers failure modes such as local buckling, intralamina and interlamina damage. A key feature of the new methodology is that it recognises the significant effect that geometric imperfections have on the localised laminate stress fields, as well as on local buckling behaviour.

KEYWORDS: compression, buckling, failure, cylindrical shells, thin-walled, acoustic emission, finite element, design

INTRODUCTION

Cylindrical shell sections are commonly used as structural members for resisting various loading configurations. In aerospace and marine applications they are often used as compression or torsion resisting spars. The use of fibre reinforced composite materials in the fabrication of such structures provides advantages which include high specific stiffness and specific strength, and good dimensional stability. Calculation of the strength of composite cylindrical shells presents a formidable task, since the failure mode is very dependent on the load distribution, geometry, imperfections, material type and laminate configuration of the structure. Depending on these parameters the mode of failure can occur at a structural level (global buckling), laminate level (local buckling, lamina in-plane fracture, delamination), or at a microstructural level (fibre buckling, kink band formation). The actual failure may also be a combination of modes, often involving interaction of different mechanisms.

The effect of geometric imperfections such as shape and thickness variations on the stability of thin shells is well documented [1]. However in the case of composite materials, localised laminate bending caused by geometric imperfections can also generate high intralamina and interlamina prebuckling stresses, resulting in damage to the laminate which may then initiate other failure modes such as buckling or delamination.

The failure mode of cylindrical shells is primarily governed by the geometry of the structure, particularly the thickness of the shell wall (t) relative to its radius of curvature (r). The compressive strength of thin-walled shells (r/t typically > 100) is normally governed by the stability of the shell wall. The prediction of the buckling load and postbuckling behaviour of such shells is reasonably well understood. Geometrically nonlinear finite element methods can be used to predict the buckling loads with an acceptable level of accuracy [2]. The modes of failure of thick-walled shells (r/t typically < 10) in compression have been identified as primarily kink band formation and delamination, although failure criteria are still in their infancy [3]. The failure of shells in the intermediate range ($10 < r/t < 100$) is not well understood.

This paper addresses failure prediction for moderately thin-walled cylinders ($r/t \approx 60$) subjected to compressive axial loads. For cylinders of such dimension the local buckling load can be of similar magnitude to the compressive strength of the laminate. The failure modes of 8 ply carbon fibre/epoxy cylinders with layup configurations $[0_2/90_2]_s$, $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$, and $[45/-45/45/-45]_s$ (subscript s designates a symmetric layup, as corresponds to antisymmetric) are characterised experimentally with the aid of acoustic emission monitoring and predicted by a finite element analysis (FEA) based design methodology. The key feature of the new methodology is that it recognises the significant effect that geometric imperfections have on the localised laminate stress fields, as well as on local buckling behaviour.

FAILURE CHARACTERISTICS

Introduction

The ability to monitor dynamically, providing a response to a discontinuity under an imposed structural stress in real time provides Acoustic Emission monitoring (AE) with a significant advantage over other nondestructive testing methods. Methods such as radiography, dye penetrant and magnetic particle techniques are not capable of continuous monitoring. Eddy current and ultrasonics, although being capable of such continuous monitoring, are not as suitable for defect monitoring because the location and direction of the defect needs to be known. AE is able to monitor relatively large regions of a structure, and with appropriate sensor location and signal processing, can be used to locate the origins of emissions. In theory, AE can be used to identify the failure type from the signal characteristics, however in the case of composite materials the characteristics of different failure modes are still not well defined. Attempts to correlate results with those from other researchers is complicated by the effect that acquisition parameters such as filtering and threshold settings have on the processed AE results. Most AE transducers also have highly nonlinear response curves, meaning that the form of the processed AE signals is very dependent on the type of transducer used. Characterisation of signals based upon spectral response is often avoided because of non-uniform absorption, dispersions, scattering and reflections. Typically the response waveform is defined and characterised by events (acoustic activity) and/or the amplitude of the signal. These two parameters were used for the characterisation of an event in this study.

Experimental Details

Carbon fibre/epoxy composite cylinders were fabricated on a 125mm diameter aluminium mandrel. The mandrel was machined and polished to tolerances of $\pm 0.01\text{mm}$ to ensure minimal geometric variation of the laminate. Three different 8 ply layups $[0_2/90_2]_s$, $[90/+45/-$

$45/0]_{AS}$ and $[+45/-45/+45/-45]_S$ were constructed from 150g/m^2 , intermediate modulus, carbon fibre/epoxy pre-impregnate (CYCOM 950-1 IM2C-150g). High strength epoxy resin (Lockfast K2001) was used to bond the samples into 2mm wide and 2mm deep grooves in machined aluminium platens. The laminates were tested with an Instron test machine (model no. 1186, 200kN) at a cross-head displacement rate of 0.5mm/min. Load was applied to the aluminium platens through steel spheres to ensure axial loading. Fig. 1 shows the experimental configuration.

*Fig.1: Experimental configuration
(Dimensions in mm)*

The acoustic emission system used was a Vallens AMS-3, 4 channel acquisition unit with Vallens SE-45 type transducers. These transducers have a sensitivity in the range of 25 to 120kHz and a secondary range of sensitivity from 130kHz to approximately 230kHz. The acoustic emission signal was bandpass filtered with a 30kHz to 1MHz preamplifier and the total system amplification maintained at 34dB allowing processing of the preamplifier input signal up to 99.9dB above 1mV ($\pm 99\text{mV}$ peak). A threshold of 36dB above 1mV ($\pm 63.1\text{mV}$ peak) was set to eliminate any background noise. Rubber bands held the transducers onto the cylinder surface during the tests with petroleum based gel being used as an acoustic coupling medium. The directional acoustic propagation characteristics of composite materials and the multiple propagation paths of a cylindrical geometry greatly complicate planar source location. In this test programme a three sensor linear transducer configuration was used to enable the axial location of events to be determined. This allowed any extraneous noise from sources such as crushing of the specimen ends and machinery related noise to be identified.

Experimental Results

Failure modes

Each of the three laminate configurations demonstrated a different mode of failure. This is graphically shown in Fig. 2, which presents the cumulative acoustic events vs. load level for typical samples of each layup. The $[0_2/90_2]_S$ specimens failed in an asymmetric local buckling type mode, with virtually no prebuckling acoustic activity. In the case of the $[90/45/-$

45/0]_{AS} laminates there was moderate acoustic activity at load levels as low as 40% of the failure load, suggesting that damage was occurring within the laminate well before the final failure which appeared to be a buckling dominated mode. The [45/-45/45/-45]_S laminates demonstrated significant acoustic activity from low load levels with a dramatic increase in the number of events as the load reached approximately 50kN. The final failure was characterised by significant localised damage to the laminate.

Fig. 2: Cumulative acoustic events vs. applied compressive load

Location of Failures

The distribution of the acoustic emissions for all specimen types indicated concentrations of emissions which corresponded well with the actual failure locations. As shown in Fig. 3, a uniform spread was observed across the remaining portion of the cylinder for the [90/45/-45/0]_{AS} and [45/-45/45/-45]_S laminates, suggesting that the mechanism generating them is related to a global laminate strength parameter rather than a consequence of a single localised imperfection or boundary constraints. Although the final failure of the [45/-45/45/-45]_S laminate (between 12-14 cm) was related to significant local bending caused by the constraining effects of the end platens, Fig. 3 (b) clearly demonstrates that damage occurred throughout the cylinder length. This figure also shows that the large cumulative number of events shown in Fig. 2 for the [45/-45/45/-45]_S case is the result of relatively few events at many positions and times during the test. The few events detected for the [02/902]_S specimens were all located at the position of the final failure.

(a) [90/45/-45/0]_{AS} (b) [45/-45/45/-45]_S

Fig. 3: Acoustic events vs. position

(The 0 position refers to the top sensor as shown in Fig. 1.

Sensors 2 and 3 are positioned down the specimen at 6 and 12cm respectively)

Failure Loads

The failure loads of the specimens are presented in Table 1. The mean strength of the $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ specimens was approximately 6% higher than that of the $[0_2/90_2]_s$, and the $[45/-45/45/-45]_s$ specimens were as anticipated, significantly weaker than the other two configurations. The failure loads for the $[45/-45/45/-45]_s$ tubes were remarkably consistent with less than 2% difference in load between each specimen. Experimental buckling failure loads, as in the case of the $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ and $[0_2/90_2]_s$ specimens, are typically subject to significant variation because of the sensitivity to variations in imperfection size. The consistency of the $[45/-45/45/-45]_s$ specimens may be related to their different failure mode, which is more dependent on material strength parameters than imperfection magnitudes.

Table 1: Failure loads

Laminate	Individual Failure Loads (kN)	Mean Failure Load (kN)
$[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$	124, 113, 128, 128, 114	121
$[0_2/90_2]_s$	117, 100	109
$[45/-45/45/-45]_s$	56, 56, 57	56

Acoustic Event Amplitude

The acoustic emissions from the $[+45/-45/+45/-45]_s$ laminate were identified as predominantly high amplitude events, typically greater than 70dB. In contrast the $[0_2/90_2]_s$ and $[90/+45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminates showed relatively few events greater than 60dB. Fig. 4 shows a typical amplitude vs. load response for a $[90/+45/-45/0]_{as}$ specimen.

Fig. 4: Amplitude of acoustic events vs. load for $[90/+45/-45/0]_{as}$ specimen (Threshold at 40dB)

FAILURE PREDICTION

Introduction

Buckling failure of thin and medium walled cylindrical shells is often predicted by using a linear eigenvalue buckling analysis. However this type of analysis does not account for the degrading effects of geometric imperfections and consequently normally over estimates the buckling load. A more accurate approach is to perturb a finite element mesh, often by using the first mode eigenvector scaled to an amplitude equivalent to that of a typical imperfection, and conduct a geometrically nonlinear analysis. Arc controlled step incrementation is usually used for such analyses because it has proved effective in negotiating limit points and snap back points associated with nonlinear buckling analyses. However because nonlinear analyses are computationally intensive, they are usually only performed if the design load is similar to the eigenvalue predicted buckling load. If buckling is not of concern for the shell, then linear FEA based stress analysis is often used to predict the failure load of the structure. The danger in using such an approach for thin or medium walled shells is that imperfections or boundary constraints can generate large local bending related stresses, which will not be accurately predicted by a linear analysis. The methodology presented in this paper focuses on the significant effect that geometric imperfections have on the localised stress fields, as well as on the local buckling behaviour. The effect of nonlinear shear stress constitutive behaviour typical of carbon fibre/epoxy composite lamina is also considered.

Methodology

A commercial FEA code (EMRC NISA) was used to model the cylinders with laminated composite quadrilateral shell elements (NKTP 32). A quarter model was constructed, with symmetric boundary conditions imposed at the two longitudinal boundaries. At the load boundary, full constraints were imposed with exception of the load translational direction, to simulate a built-in end as in the experimental tests. The load was applied to the shell as a nodal force at the load boundary through rigid links, simulating a centrally loaded rigid plate. A convergence study confirmed that the mesh of 200 elements (3846 degrees of freedom) was adequately refined to accurately model the buckling load and mode.

Several types of analyses were conducted to assess the accuracy of alternative finite element modeling approaches for the prediction of compressive load carrying ability. A suitable methodology must be able to accurately predict the failure load of the structure, whether it fails by buckling, material fracture, or a combination of both. Analysis alternatives included linear FEA based stress analysis, linear eigenvalue extraction for both perfect and perturbed meshes, geometrically nonlinear stress and buckling analyses, and nonlinear analyses including material nonlinearity in shear.

The most successful approach proved to be a multi-analysis scheme, beginning with a linear eigenvalue analysis to predict a buckling load and mode shape. The initial mesh was then perturbed into a shape based on the first mode eigenvector, and the maximum load for the nonlinear analysis set to the predicted eigenvalue load. In this study the perturbation magnitudes were based on measured geometric properties of the experimental specimens (a maximum amplitude of 10% of the wall thickness), however in the absence of such data it would be necessary to estimate a likely perturbation based on expected production tolerances. Geometrically nonlinear analyses were then performed using arc controlled step incrementation. Experimentation with step control and convergence parameters were usually

required to achieve stable solutions. The predicted stress levels within each ply were then assessed with the FEA software's postprocessor, both to check if material fracture was likely prior to buckling failure, and also to determine the level of intralamina shear stresses. In cases where the predicted shear stress levels were significant (in excess of 30 MPa in this case), nonlinear analyses were performed with nonlinear lamina shear stiffness properties. The stress levels within the laminates were then reassessed.

The accuracy of alternative failure criteria for composite materials remains a topic of considerable debate. This study employed the simple “maximum stress” criterion, which has the advantage of simplicity while appearing to have some degree of correlation with experimental results [4]. The critical stress component for both the $[+45/-45/+45/-45]_s$ and $[90/+45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminates proved to be the intralamina shear of the $\pm 45^\circ$ laminae, while the $[0_2/90_2]_s$ case was predicted to fail in a buckling mode before any stress component became critical. Software limitations prevented the calculation of interlamina stresses from the results of the nonlinear analyses, however these were assessed from linear analyses of perturbed meshes, and by creating quasi-three-dimensional models from beams and shells, as proposed by Nishiwaki et al. [5]. Interlamina stresses did not appear to be critical for these laminates and loading condition.

Results

Deformations

The load vs. deflection curves determined for each laminate from the geometrically nonlinear analyses are shown in Fig. 5. A postbuckling response was predicted for the $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminate, however numerical difficulties were encountered at the bifurcation point for the other two laminates. All three curves show a well defined nonlinear region, confirming the need for a geometrically nonlinear analysis. The analyses which failed to follow the load deflection behaviour into the stable postbuckling region are a result of the structure approaching zero stiffness at the point of buckling and the governing matrix becoming singular. In practice the analytical postbuckling responses were not realised experimentally because the large strains incurred in the postbuckling region result in laminate failure which is not simulated in the analysis. Fig. 6 shows the deformations of the $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminate, illustrating the change from pre- to postbuckling deformation mode and the resulting large deformations that are predicted.

Fig. 5: Nonlinear buckling load deflection responses

(a) Prebuckled

(b) Postbuckled

Fig. 6: Prebuckled and postbuckled deformed shapes for $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminate

Effect of Material Nonlinearities

The $[90/+45/-45/0]_{as}$ and $[0_2/90_2]_s$ experimental load-deflection curves followed the same basic shape as the FEA predictions. However as shown in Fig. 7, the experimental curve for the $[+45/-45/+45/-45]_s$ case diverges from the geometrically nonlinear predictions at a load of approximately 25 kN. This load corresponds to the onset of acoustic emissions, as shown in Fig. 2, and corresponds to FEA predictions of maximum shear stresses of approximately 30 MPa. As the shear stiffness of these types of materials is typically significantly nonlinear, combined material and geometric nonlinear models were created which used a nonlinear shear stress behaviour for the laminae. The exact shear stiffness characteristics for the material were not available, so generic data was used with the initial modulus scaled to match the previous linear material properties. Numerical difficulties at yield prevented results being obtained from a piecewise nonlinear shear model, however modeling the shear behaviour as bilinear was more successful as shown in Fig. 7. The results should be regarded as only indicative since the material stiffness and yield parameters are estimated, and the bilinear model was unable to model the shear stress behaviour of the material through to final failure. However correlation with the experimental results is greatly improved for the initial part of the experimental curve, demonstrating that the nonlinear shear behaviour of the material is a significant factor in the global response of the cylinders.

Fig. 7: Effects of shear nonlinearity on buckling load predictions for $[+45/-45/+45/-45]_s$ specimen

Predicted Stress Levels

There was very good correlation between the onset of acoustic emissions and high predicted shear stresses for the $[90/+45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminates. Fig. 8 shows contour plots of the shear stresses within the most highly loaded lamina. At a load of 64.5 kN which corresponds to the onset of acoustic emissions the maximum shear stress is approximately 30 MPa, while at 117 kN which corresponds to the final mixed mode failure of the cylinders the predicted shear stress is approximately 86 MPa. For the $[+45/-45/+45/-45]_s$ case the onset of acoustic emissions also correlates with a predicted shear stress of approximately 30 MPa and the maximum predicted shear stress at failure is approximately 83 MPa.

(a) Layer 7 at 64.5 kN

(b) Layer 7 at 117 kN

Fig. 8: Shear stress contours for $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ laminate

Failure Loads

Table 2 summarises the predicted and measured failure loads for each specimen. The linear FEA (LFEA) laminate failure models apply the maximum stress failure criterion to a linear static analysis, and the LFEA buckling results refer to a linear eigenvalue analysis. The main limitation of the linear analyses is that they do not consider the increases in bending stresses and reductions in stability which occur as deflections and rotations of the shell wall increase. The critical failure loads predicted by the nonlinear FEA (NLFEA) for each laminate type are highlighted, and correlate well with the experimental results. In the $[90/45/-45/0]_{as}$ case the predicted load for laminate failure (maximum stress criterion) is almost exactly the same as that for a buckling failure, which supports the experimental observations of a mixed mode failure. The poorest correlation is for the $[0_2/90_2]_s$ specimens, for which the buckling failure load is very sensitive to imperfection magnitude and only limited experimental data was available.

Table 2: Predicted failure loads

Laminate	Laminate Failure		Buckling		Load	Experimental Mode
	LFEA	NLFEA	LFEA	NLFEA		
[90/45/-45/0] _{as}	226	117	171	120	121	Laminate and Buckling
[02/902] _s	318	>98	120	98	109	Buckling
[45/-45/45/-45] _s	62	53	130	108	56	Laminate

CONCLUSIONS

Each of the laminate configurations demonstrated a different mode of failure. The [02/902]_s specimens failed in an asymmetric local buckling mode, with virtually no prebuckling acoustic activity. In the case of the [90/45/-45/0]_{as} laminates there was moderate acoustic activity at load levels as low as 40% of the final failure load, suggesting that damage was occurring within the laminate well before the final failure in a buckling related mode. The [45/-45/45/-45]_s demonstrated significant acoustic activity from low load levels and failed in a material fracture mode.

Nonlinear finite element analyses demonstrated that geometric imperfections and constraint effects result in localised bending deformations which generate high intralamina stresses, particularly as inplane shear within the 45° plies. The nonlinear shear behaviour of the laminae also influences the stress fields within the shells, particularly for the +/-45° laminate. The load at failure of the [02/902]_s specimens correlated well with nonlinear FEA predictions of local buckling.

The onset of acoustic emissions from the [90/45/-45/0]_{as} specimens appears to be related to intralamina shear failures within some of the 45° laminae. The final failure of these specimens occurred at loads close to those predicted by nonlinear FEA buckling analyses suggesting that the prebuckling damage did not significantly degrade the laminate stiffness. The [45/-45/45/-45]_s cylinders failed at a load corresponding to shear failure of the laminae, at a load of approximately 50% of the predicted buckling load. The proposed design methodology accurately predicted the mode and failure load of each of the laminates. The key feature of the methodology is that it recognises the significant effect that geometric imperfections have on the localised laminate stress fields, as well as on local buckling behaviour.

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